

Effect of a “Stochastic” Potential in Bound State Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes, we argued one may formulate bound state quantum mechanics by assuming a stochastic potential which delivers “hits” of momentum k $V(k) \exp(ikx)$, while having an average form of $V(x)$. A main constraint seems to be that the different k $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ hits may occur at any x point and that $V(x)$ be of the form $\text{Sum over } k \text{ } b(kx)$ so that $-d/dx b(kx) = -k b(kx)$. In other words, conservation of energy exists at the level of each hit as well as for the overall average. To force all of these constraints, a solution of $b(kx)=V(k) \exp(ikx)$ emerges which introduces periodicity and complex numbers. It should be noted that $V(x)= \text{Sum } V(k) \exp(ikx)$ so each term is actually a “piece of potential energy”. Furthermore, we argue that $V(x)$ is decomposed for physical reasons i.e. $V(x)$ is a low resolution result which incorporates all of the “pieces”. In a quantum mechanical situation, a “piece” $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ may act at t_1 and $V(k_2)\exp(i k_2x)$ at t_2 . We argue that $\exp(ikx)$ should have physical meaning and leads to $\sin(kx)$ terms for the “ k ” and “ $-k$ ” pieces. Thus, there is forward and backward motion which “cancel” i.e. have nothing to do with $V(x)$. For a particle, however, in this region, there may be forward and backward motion, both of which have kinetic energy which should not be part of the average kinetic energy at x . The various physical (resolved) pieces of the potential lead to momentum distribution at each x point with $P(p/x)= a(p) \exp(ipx)/ W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction). In this case, one has a probability, not “pieces” of $KE(x)$. At first, one may be alarmed by complex probabilities, but they are necessary to allow for cancellation of kinetic energy pieces due to the positive/negative values combined $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ pieces. Thus, even though $KE(x)$ (average) matches classical results, the actual motion is more complicated.

The potential seems to be the driver of the ensemble picture and should be linked to the microscopic physical nature of the potential. In this note, we wish to examine features and consequences of such a stochastic potential, including the idea of tunneling and infinite potential walls.

Stochastic Potential and Conservation of Energy

In classical physics, one applies conservation of energy for conservative forces. If one considers a stochastic potential or a “highly resolved” potential with an average value of $V(x)$, then conservation of energy should exist at each x point on average, as well as for each hit which delivers “ k ” momentum times $V(k) \exp(ikx)$.

In classical physics, a specific k_i hit of momentum occurs in each Δx region, but for the quantum stochastic case, any k hit may occur, albeit with a certain weight. The physical consequences are serious for such a picture because it seems to imply: (A) the potential contains a large amount of energy if it can deliver a large k hit, even rarely and (B) a bound particle although having an average momentum at x has a small probability of having a very large momentum which is useful for tunneling.

Idea (A) is not a problem if part of the force delivered by $-d/dx V(k)\exp(ikx)$ cancels with part of the force delivered by $-d/dx V(j) \exp(i jx)$. $V(x)$ is simply the “sum” of these pieces, it does not

give the “whole” picture. For example, $F_1 + F_1 = 2F_1 - F_1$. Thus, there may be underlying microscopic scenarios yielding the same “total” force result of $2F_1$. For a classical particle, one apparently does not worry because the various “pieces” even if acting at different times, act within a very tiny overall Δt (in the classical time frame), thus the classical particle only sees the overall force within Δx and the final kinetic energy (not an average kinetic energy which could actually involve forward and backward motion for tiny amounts of time).

Furthermore, assuming that a hit of k $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ momentum may occur at any x also has serious consequences if one insists that $-d/dx b(kx) = -k \text{function}(kx)$. $\text{function}(kx)$ must “build” the average $F(x)$ and so having it grow and decrease with x may be problematic. This leads to the idea of periodicity or $\exp(ipx)$ which is both periodic and complex. Periodicity with a real function for $b(kx)$ would lead to a result such as $\sin(kx)$ or $\cos(kx)$ which depends specifically on x (in magnitude) which one does not want. The result $\exp(ikx)$ for $+k$ may be combined with $-k$ for $\exp(-ikx)$ to yield a real $\sin(kx)$ or $\cos(kx)$, but this represents averaging at different times. Thus, if one has $a(p) = a(-p)$ or $a(p) = a(-p)$, it may appear that $p^2/2m \sin(px)$ or $p^2/2m \cos(px)$ may have negative values which is unusual, but these are a consequence of averaging at different times.

Given that the potential is written as:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k) \exp(ikx) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{each } V(k)\exp(ikx) \text{ is actually a “piece” of potential.}$$

To use ((1a)) in the first place, one must assume these periodic pieces are physical. It is assumed the different pieces act at different times, but part of the force created by one may cancel part of the force created by another. For example, if $V(k) = V(-k)$ then the “ k ” and “ $-k$ ” pieces yield $2 V(k) \cos(kx)$ which is positive for some x values and negative for others even if the overall $V(x)$ is strictly positive. Thus, physically there may be back and forth motion of a particle even though $-d/dx V(x)$ (the total force) is strictly positive and such motion should not occur “classically”. As a result, some kinetic energy stirred up by these pieces should not be part of $KE(x)$ average. This suggests there must be a way to allow portions of a quantum particle’s actual kinetic energy to cancel to produce a proper $KE(x)$ average. This is an unusual situation and leads to periodic $\exp(ipx)$ terms in the momentum distribution’s probabilities $P(p/x)$. Thus, complex probability seems to indicate motion “outside” the “average value” (KE or force) realm. As a result, complex periodic probabilities are not “overly” disturbing, but have consequences on spatial density.

The driver of quantum mechanical bound states seems to be the unusual physical nature of the potential $V(x)$. Having a momentum distribution (ensemble) at each x given by: $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{normalization constant} = \text{wavefunction}$ follows as a consequence. The Schrodinger equation is then the average conservation of energy at x i.e.

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p) \ exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1b))$$

In (1), we develop arguments for $P(p/x)$ being of the form $a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$.

Here E is an average energy and conservation of energy occurs for each microscopic stochastic hit as well. Energy uncertainty with Δt seems to apply to the average energy and changes in the ensemble in time. Time in the uncertainty principle does not seem to be used to follow the motion of a particle as each $\exp(ipx)$ in ((1)) occurs at a different time.

Here we stress that unlike the potential which is a sum of $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ pieces, the kinetic energy is an average. The kinetic energy is still $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ for a particle at x at an instant t_i . These averages, however, must remove back and forth kinetic energy stirred up by back and forth forces e.g. $2V(k) \cos(kx)$ which ultimately cancel portions of other potential "pieces" $2V(j) \cos(jx)$. Thus, by having physical force or potential pieces which may partially cancel when creating $V(x)$, the quantum motion is very different from the classical average $KE(x)$. Complex periodic probability weights for $P(p/x)$ allow for such cancellation, but suggest actual physical motion of a quantum particle (and hence its density) is very different than that is suggested by average motion i.e. $KE(x)$.

Furthermore, the statement that the wavefunction for a free electron is $\exp(ipx)$ may be a consequence of a potential which occurs when the electron is either created or "initiated". If the form $\exp(ipx)$ emerges when an electron is created (say pair production), then $\exp(ipx)$ may be the consequence of the physical behaviour of electrons. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from a bound state potential $V(x)$, may also be consistent with "free" electron behaviour suggesting an underlying relationship between the microscopic behaviour of a potential and an elementary particle.

Fourier Transform of $V(x)$

It is argued above that $V(x)$ is in a sense stochastic and may give hits of momentum k $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ at any point x . Microscopically, there is conservation of energy as well as conservation of energy holding for average values. In particular: $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. This means, however, that $V(k)$ is a Fourier transform: $V(k) = \text{constant Integral } dx V(x) \exp(-ikx)$. Thus, the weight of each k $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ momentum hit incorporates information about $V(x) \exp(-ikx)$ integrated over the whole region. Thus, these stochastic hits which at first appear to have weights $V(k)$ which yield $V(x)$ at each x , also contain global information about $V(x)$. Thus, $V(x)$ as a stochastic entity seems to be itself in a kind of "equilibrium" in which its stochastic hits at any local point are in keeping with its global nature. This may explain why bound quantum solutions appear to be resonances throughout the entire x region. [If a potential is in a kind of equilibrium throughout a region of x and $V(k)$ at each point x is based on the entire range of $V(x) \exp(-ikx)$ and this equilibrium is altered (by changing $V(x)$ in some areas), it seems signals should be sent throughout the potential.] Similarly, $a(p)$ in ((1b)) is: $\text{constant Integral } dx \exp(-ipx) W(x)$ where spatial density $= W^*(x)W(x)$, so $a(p)$, which is used in a local context, actually contains information about the global spatial density arrangement.

Wavefunction at Endpoints

In quantum mechanics, the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ integrated over x must yield 1, so $W(x)$ must approach 0 at the endpoints. We have argued in previous notes that $W^*(x)W(x)$ considers pairs of $B(p_1, p_2) = a(p_1)\exp(-ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ which occur successively in Δx . $W(x)$ itself is an average of complex probabilities $\exp(i p_i x) a(p_i)$ taken at different times and so this average and hence spatial density may drop to zero, but the complex term $B(p_i, p_j)$ does not. Furthermore, if one multiplies ((1)) by $W(x)$ (the Schrodinger equation) and writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k V(k) a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) should hold for all x , even at the endpoints. It may be noted that $V(k)$ is a Fourier transform and so incorporates information about the potential at all x points as: $V(k) = \int dx V(x) \exp(-ikx)$. If $V(x)$ is very low in two adjacent regions separated by a barrier, $V(k)$ mainly describes the barrier, yet ((2)) holds for all x because the resonance exists within the entire two regions and barrier. Similarly, for a particle with a box with zero potential except at the walls where the potential is infinite, $V(k)$ describes the walls and $a(p)$ has values for all p even though there exists a $\langle p \text{ average} \rangle = 2n \cdot 3.14/L$ and a wavefunction $\sin(p \text{ave } x)$. The wavefunction is the ensemble average taken at different times and does not describe the full dynamic picture at each time t which exists for the quantum particle.

Thus, ensemble averages taken at different times may yield $W(x \text{ endpoint})$ almost 0 and spatial density ($x \text{ endpoint}$) almost 0, but the complex relative probabilities for each p are still present and ((2)) the cycling equation still holds. This seems to be related to situations for which one has a region with a small potential followed by a barrier followed by a region with a low potential. The wavefunction $W(x)$ may become very small (dropping exponentially) within the barrier, but then may then appear with regular cycling within the second region. The cycling holds at x points ((2)), but $V(k)$ incorporates information about the potential throughout the entire spatial region, so the hits of momentum k at any x point have a weight based on an integral of $V(x) \exp(-ikx)$ throughout.

(This has been tested experimentally in tunneling type experiments.) Thus, it may be that physical features are present within the stochastic model (i.e. various momenta) and that it is not simply the ensemble averages (taken at different times) which yield physical information. For example, tunneling and the presence of cycling in both low potential regions seem to be linked more closely to a stochastic momentum distribution (albeit with complex probabilities) than to ensemble averages such as $W(x)$ or $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Tunneling and Infinite Potential

If a stochastic potential is able to give different momentum hits, then a particle may have a range of momenta over time. Some of these may be large enough to penetrate barriers.

Furthermore, given the stochastic nature or hits from a potential, a particle should be able to penetrate a little into any barrier because there is a probability for a low k hit at the barrier. In the case of an infinite potential, one may argue that the idea of having k hits for all x no longer holds, but $-d/dx b(kx)$ still holds. Furthermore, an infinite potential should also be stochastic, rendering various momentum hits. Thus, for a particle in a box, even though $\sin(p\text{-ave } x)$ may solve the Schrodinger equation, $p\text{-ave}$ is only an average momentum as noted in the literature. At the walls, various momenta may be stirred up due to the stochastic nature of potentials.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one were able to apply “high resolution” to a potential $V(x)$ one would see that it is actually composed of pieces $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ which in the quantum situation may act at different times. These correspond to different force pieces which may partially cancel to yield the total $-dV/dx$, but nevertheless stir up forward backward motion of a particle. Because one $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ may act at x at time t_1 and another $V(k_2)\exp(i k_2 x)$ at t_2 , a momentum distribution arises. Physically there should be forward and backward motion with corresponding kinetic energy which is “outside” of $KE(\text{average})$. Thus, complex probabilities $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ allow for cancellations of some of this “extra” kinetic energy. It should be noted that the average $\text{Sum over } p P(p/x) p^2/2m$ picks up kinetic energy values at different times and so accounts for all kinetic energy motion. For example, if $a(p)=a(-p)$ then the terms for p and $-p$ yield $2a(p) \cos(px)$ which is positive in some regions and negative in others. The contribution to the average kinetic energy is: $p^2/2m 2a(p) \cos(px)$ so there is actually a “negative” contribution to the average kinetic energy (which removes the “extra” motion) for some x . This, however, also has consequences on the quantum spatial density which follows from $W^*(x)W(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Joint Conditional Probability and the Bound Quantum Density (preprint, zenodo, 2020)